

DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS ON BUYING BEHAVIOR OF PACKAGED MILK - A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO MAYILADUTHURAI TOWN

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Abstract

The goal of this paper is to examine the buying preference of branded packaged milk in Mayiladuthurai town. How the demographic factors such as age, sex, education, income, occupation, etc. will influence the behavior of pattern of buying packaged milk.

Introduction

Indian economy has grown over the years successfully crossing various barriers, but the benefits did not flow evenly to all regions or various sections of the people. This statement goes to strengthen the saying that all out efforts in the past has led the rich to become richer and poor to become poorer. The condition is even more acute in rural India, where a vast majority of out population is still living below poverty line. The main occupation continues to be agriculture, which continues to contribute significantly to the National income of our economy. Increasing suicide deaths of agriculturist, in many parts our country convey their sorry state of affairs. Vast majorities of the agriculturist are landless agricultural labourers or marginal farmers with small land holding live with meager income earned through seasonal agricultural activities. This situation is confirmed by the fact that 42% of the rural population is still in poverty.

Objectives of the study:

The study indicates the following objectives are,

1. To understand the demographic profile of the sample respondents.
2. To ascertain the brand preference towards the different kinds of packaged milk.
3. To summarize the various findings and to offer suitable suggestions for improving branded packaged milk.

Methodology:

To achieve the above mentioned objectives, the required data were collected from both

primary and secondary sources. To elicit the required primary data collected well structured questionnaire from 80 sample respondents in the study area of mayiladuthurai town by adopting convenience sampling method. The required secondary data were collected from various websites, books, magazines and journals.

Limitations of the study:

The present study indicates some of the limitations.

1. The present study covers a region of mayiladuthurai town only.
2. Only 100 sample respondents were taken into study.
3. The study incorporates primary data obtained through questionnaire, the reliability of the information depends on the correctness of the data provided by the respondents.

Analysis and Discussion

Table 1: Age wise classification

Age (in years)	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Below 20 years	15	15
20 – 30 years	25	25
30 – 40 years	26	26
40 – 50 years	18	18
Above 50 years	16	16
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

It is observed from the above table 1 indicates the age wise classification of the sample respondents, out of 100 samples, 26 respondents were belonged to the age group of 30-40 years, 18 respondents were belonged to the 40 – 50 years, 25 respondents were 20 – 30 years, 18 respondents were above 50 years and 15 respondents were belonged to the age group of below 20 years respectively.

Table 2: Gender wise classification

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	41	41
Female	59	59
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

It is witnessed from the above table 2, it clearly explains the gender wise classification of the

respondents, majority of the respondents were constituted female and the rest were constituted male.

Table3: Educationwise classification

Education	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Illiterate	22	22
Upto HSC	34	34
Degree	30	30
Others	14	14
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

It can be observed from the table 3 the education wise classification of the respondents, out of 100 sample respondents 34 respondents were completed their education upto HSC level, 22 persons were illiterate, 30 respondents were degree holders and 14 respondents were technically qualified in the category of others.

Table :4 Occupation wise classification

Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Household	26	26
Govt. employee	24	24
Private	19	19
Businessman	15	15
Others	16	16
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

From the table 4, it reveals that the occupation of the sample size, it was inferred that the 26%(26) of the respondents were households, 19% (19) of the respondents were working in the private concerns, 16% (16) respondents were doing self-employed and 24% (24) of the respondents were government employees.

Table :5 Income wise classification

Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Below 5000	17	17
5000 – 20000	30	30
20000 – 35000	22	22
35000 – 50000	18	18
Above 50000	13	13
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

It is observed from the table 5, income wise classification of the respondents, out of 100 samples, 30 respondents were belonged to the income group of 5000-20000, 22 respondents were 20000-35000, 18 respondents were 35000-50000, 17 respondents were belonged to below 5000 and 13 respondents were belonged to the income group of above 50000.

Table 6: Marital status

Marital status	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Married	78	78
Unmarried	22	22
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

From the table 4, it was inferred that the marital status of the sample respondents, out of 100 samples, majority of the respondents were married who were constituted 78% (78) and the rest of the respondents were unmarried who were constituted 22% (22).

Table 7: Brand Preference towards different kinds of packaged milk

Brand choice	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Aavin	25	25
Arockiya	28	28
KC	16	16
Tamil	14	14
Hatsun	17	17
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

From the table 7, it shows the brand preference of packaged milk by the consumers of mayiladuthurai town, it depicts that the out of 100 sample respondents, 28 respondents were preferred to consume Arockiya were considerably higher than the preference of (25) Aavin, 17 respondents were prefer to consume Hatsun, 16 respondents were prefer KC and the remaining 11 respondents were prefer to consume Tamil packaged milk.

Table 8: opinion about price, taste and package of different kinds of packaged milk

Particulars	Taste	Price	Package
Highly satisfied	24	24	32
Satisfied	42	40	38
Neutral	24	20	16
Dissatisfied	08	14	10
Highly dissatisfied	02	02	-
Total	100	100	100

Source: Primary Data

From the table 8, it depicts the consumer’s opinion about price, taste and package of different kinds of packaged milk, majority of the respondents opined about the taste was satisfied by their brand preferred and 24 respondents were highly satisfied about their brand preferred. It was observed from the table 8 opinion about the price of the different kinds of brands, most of the (40) consumers satisfied their brand price, 24 were highly satisfied their brand price and 02 respondents were dissatisfied. It was inferred that the table depicts the opinion about the package of the different brands, 42 respondents and 40 respondents were satisfied the quality of packaging of their preferred brands respectively.

Findings:

1. From the table 1, majority of the respondents were belonged to the age group of 30 to 40 years.
2. 59 respondents were constituted female respondents out of 100 samples
3. 34% of the respondents were completed their education was upto HSC level.
4. Majority of the respondents were 26% households.
5. 22 respondents were belonged to the income group of 5000 – 20000.
6. 78% respondents were constituted married in the study.
7. out of 100 samples, 28 respondents were preferred to consume Arockiya packaged milk.
8. 42 respondents were opined satisfied about taste by consuming their preferred brand.

Suggestions:

1. The packaged milk producers should reduce the selling price to meet out the competing producers.
2. The packaged milk producer should make more number of advertisements to retain his customers.
3. To make periodical review to analyse the product condition.
4. Innovative thinking of package must be practiced.
5. To arrange festival offer to attract the households.

Conclusion

The study reveals the brand preference of packaged milk producers in Mayiladuthurai town. It clearly indicates the variety of reason influence to select the buying of packaged milk by the consumers. Milk producers must meet consumers' demand for milk when there is demand in order to remain competitive. Once we are able to clearly describe the existing demand for milk, a marketing strategy can be properly developed.

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